

Hypervalent Iodine in Organic Synthesis : Convenient and General Procedures for α -Functionalisation of Ketones

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In recent years, the utility of hypervalent iodine reagents has remained one of the most fascinating areas of organic synthesis. The great attention has been focussed on the I(III) mediated oxidation reactions of enolisable ketones yielding α -functionalised ketones¹⁻⁴. One of the extremely useful observation from our recent reports is the importance of α -tosyloxyketones (**2**), readily accessible from the oxidation of ketones (**1**) using [hydroxy(tosyloxy)iodo]benzene (HTIB) over α -halogenoketones²⁻⁷. Encouraged by these results, we applied similar approach for the synthesis of α -aroyloxyacetophenones (**3**) and α -aroxyacetophenones (**4**). The results on the synthesis of **3** and **4** alongwith the modification of experimental procedure for α -tosyloxyacetophenones (**2**)² thereby providing improved procedures for the other α -functionalised acetophenones^{3,4} are reported here.

Results and Discussion

Acetophenones (**1a-d**) were oxidised with HTIB in acetonitrile according to the literature method^{2,3} (condition i). α -Tosyloxyacetophenones (**2a-d**) thus obtained in situ on treatment with sodium benzoate in absolute ethanol containing 2-3 drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ (condition iii) afforded α -benzyloxyacetophenones (**3a-d**) in moderate yields (29-55%, method I). Use of triethylamine and aromatic carboxylic acids in acetonitrile (condition iv) in place of condition iii, simplified the procedure thereby giving **3a-e** in much better yields (56-67%, method II).

Aroxyacetophenones (**4a-f**) were prepared by

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) HTIB/CH₃CN, (ii) IBD-PTSA/CH₃CN, (iii) Ar¹COONa/EtOH, (iv) Ar¹COOH-Et₃N, (v) Ar²OH-anh. K₂CO₃/dry acetone, (vi) Ar³NH₂, (vii) KSCN.
Ar, Ar¹, Ar², Ar³ = Phenyl or *p*-substituted phenyl.

treating **2** (generated in situ from **1**) with phenols in dry acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate. The procedure to generate **2** was further simplified by using iodobenzene diacetate (IBD)-*p*-toluenesulphonic acid (PTSA) (HTIB is generated in situ, condition ii) instead of HTIB (condition i). This modification in the procedure of obtaining **2**, automatically offered the simpler method for other α -functionalised ketones (**3-6**) which involves **2** in their syntheses.

It must be mentioned that α -functionalised acetophenones (**2-6**), available from this approach, are valuable precursors for the synthesis of a wide variety of heterocyclic compounds. Thus the present study not only simplifies the existing synthesis of **2** \rightarrow **6**, but also offers a new and convenient methodology for various heterocycles such as thiazoles^{4,6,7}, imidazoles⁸ and oxazoles⁹

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries

and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 842 IR spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

α -Aroyloxyacetophenones (3a-e) : *Method I. General procedure :* To a solution of an acetophenone (**1**; 2.5 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 ml), HTIB (1 g, 2.55 mmol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. After removing the solvent by distillation, sodium benzoate (0.36 g, 2.5 mmol) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) containing concentrated H_2SO_4 (2 drops) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6–8 h. Dilution with water (50 ml) gave a gummy solid which was extracted with chloroform (3×20 ml). Removal of the solvent from the organic phase followed by crystallisation with ethanol gave **3** (Table 1).

Method II. General procedure : An acetophenone (**1**; 2.5 mol) was treated with HTIB (2.55 mmol) in acetonitrile according to method I. After cooling the solution, benzoic acid (0.305 g, 2.5 mmol) and triethylamine (0.35 ml, 2.5 mmol) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 1–3 h. The solvent was removed by distillation and ethanol (10 ml) was added. Compound **3** separated out as crystalline solid on chilling the above solution was filtered and washed with ethanol.

α -Aroxyacetophenones (4a-f). General procedure : After treating acetophenone (**1**; 2.5 mmol) with HTIB (1 g, 2.55 mmol) as in method I, the solvent was removed by distillation and the mixture was refluxed with phenol (2.5 mmol) in dry acetone (20 ml) in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 (0.345 g, 2.5 mmol) for 8–12 h. Addition of water (50 ml) gave a gummy solid which was extracted with chloroform (3×20 ml). Removal of the solvent from the organic layer followed by crystallisation with ethanol afforded **4** (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **3** AND **4**

Compd. no.	Ar	Ar ¹ /Ar ²	M.p. (°C) (lit. m.p.)	Yield %
3a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	119–20 (119) ^a	67
b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	118–19 ^b	67
c	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	113 (108) ^c	60
d	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	144 ^b	56
e	C ₆ H ₅	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	126–29 ^b	62
4a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	72–74 (71–72) ^d	17
b	C ₆ H ₅	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	150–51 (156.5) ^e	31
c	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	82–84 (83–84) ^f	36
d	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	72–73 (72.5) ^g	35
e	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	134 ^b	47
f	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	163 (156–57) ^h	30

^aRef. 10. ^bThese compounds are reported in literature; since their m.ps. were not available, they were characterised by correct elemental analyses and ir and nmr spectral data : **3b** (Ref. 16) ν_{max} 1739 (O–C=O) and 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 5.34 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.9–8.1 (9H, m, ArH); **3d** (Ref. 17) ν_{max} 1728 (O–C=O) and 1708 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 5.44 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.84–8.50 (9H, m, ArH); **3e** (Ref. 17) ν_{max} 1725 (O–C=O) and 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 5.61 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.23–8.47 (9H, m, ArH); **4e** (Ref. 18) ν_{max} 1703 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.10 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.10–7.85 (8H, m, ArH). ^cref. 11. ^dRef. 12. ^eRef. 13a. ^fRef. 14. ^gRef. 13b. ^hRef. 15.

Improved procedures for 2–6 using IBD-p-TsOH.H₂O :

α -Tosyloxyacetophenone (2a) : To the suspension of IBD (0.84 g, 2.6 mmol) in acetonitrile (10 ml), was added a hot solution of *p*-TsOH.H₂O (0.9 g, 5.2 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 ml) with shaking. The resulting yellow solution was boiled for 5 min and cooled. Acetophenone (**1a**; 0.3 g, 2.5 mmol) was added to it and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. Solvent was then removed by distillation and ethanol (2–3 ml) was added. The product (**2a**) crystallised out on scratching with glass rod, was washed with ethanol, (56%), m.p. 98° (lit.². 91–92°).

Other α -functionalised acetophenones (3–6) : In this approach, **2a** generated in situ as mentioned in the above method, was treated with appropriate reagent according to the procedure described in individual class of compounds (3–6).

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